

MANUFACTURING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE PARTS BY COMBINED FILAMENT WINDING AND INJECTION MOLDING

Frank Hauptert, Chaogang Chen, Klaus Friedrich,
Institute for Composite Materials, Ltd., University of Kaiserslautern,
PO Box 3049, D - 67653 Kaiserslautern, Germany

ABSTRACT

In the frame of this work, a new possibility for manufacturing complex structural parts from thermoplastic composite materials is presented. These parts were produced by combined thermoplastic filament winding and injection molding. A filament wound part was used as an insert and in a second manufacturing step injected around with a thermoplastic material. For both techniques the processing parameters were optimized in order to achieve both, a good consolidation and impregnation quality of the filament wound insert and optimum material properties of the thermoplastic around the insert. A further criterion for the part quality was the bonding between the insert and the injected material.

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites are predestinated for low weight and high stiffness constructions. New developments have also focused on the use of thermoplastic matrices, because of their advantageous mechanical properties, especially the improved toughness.

One possibility of manufacturing thermoplastic composites is filament winding. In the frame of this work, a thermoplastic filament winding arrangement was built up, especially for processing flexible fiber bundles [1, 2]. The winding process is called in-situ-consolidation process. In order to characterize the consolidation and impregnation quality, new material testing methods, especially for thermoplastic filament wound rings had to be developed. The values of interlaminar shear strength [3], density, flexural modulus, and residual stresses were chosen as quality criteria [4]. An optimal processing window was determined by systematically varying the different winding parameters. Thermoplastic filament winding allowed the production of continuous fiber reinforced structures such as rings with a defined fiber orientation and a high fiber volume content.

The second processing method used in this study is the injection molding technology which allows the production of very complex geometries even with short fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite materials. The disadvantage of this technique is that only short fibers can be processed, and furthermore, the fiber orientation is dependent on the mold geometry and the injection parameters like temperature and pressure.

The combination of these two techniques (Fig. 1) with optimized processing parameters permits the fabrication of structural parts with complex geometries and functional properties.

Figure 1: Combination of filament winding and injection molding

DESCRIPTION OF WINDING EQUIPMENT AND PARAMETERS

The possibility of welding continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics enables the combination of two manufacturing steps, i. e. filament winding and consolidation, in one continuous production process. Filament winding of composite materials with thermoplastic matrices is more complicated than wet winding of thermosetting composites, due to the higher viscosity of thermoplastics. In the frame of this work a filament winding arrangement was especially optimized for realizing winding speeds up to 30 m/min. During this process, the incoming yarn had to be melt impregnated and immediately consolidated onto the previously wound surface at the lay down point (nip point).

The in situ filament winding device is shown in Fig. 2. A two axis motion controller coordinated the mandrel's rotation and the movement of the support to which the tow guidance system was attached. Hence, a predetermined fiber path could be realized. Tow tension was measured and controlled. A defined compaction force was applied by employing a compaction roller, or a temperature controlled sliding shoe.

Figure 2: Thermoplastic filament winding device

The melting of the tow material was realized in the following way: The raw material bobbin was positioned in a prewarming chamber (Fig. 2), which raised the temperature of the tow in front of the preheating zone. The possible prewarming temperatures were between room temperature and

200°C. The difference between the raw material temperature and the matrix material's melting temperature was significantly reduced. After leaving the prewarming chamber, the tow passed a hot air preheating zone with a length of 1 meter. The air temperature in the preheating zone was between 100°C and 500°C. The final heating arrangement was at the nip point area, which consisted of two hot air guns, the first one heating the incoming yarn, the second one the previously wound surface. An infrared line heater provided a constant nip point temperature. The mandrel temperature was also measured and controlled. Measurements of the ring surface temperatures were carried out by two pyrometers. The first one was focused at the nip point, the second one at the incoming surface of the wound part before reaching the hot air zone.

In this arrangement, the filament winding parameters were: winding speed (v_w), mandrel temperature (T_M), nip point temperature (T_{NP}), preheating temperature (T_{PH}), prewarming temperature (T_{PW}), consolidation force (F_C), and tow tension (F_T).

INJECTION MOLDING EQUIPMENT AND PARAMETERS

In this study a commercially available fully hydraulic injection molding machine (ARBURG ALLROUNDER® 270 V) was used. The machine is equipped with a SELOGICA® process control system.

The most important processing parameters were the temperature of the molten thermoplastic, the mold temperature, the injection pressure, the injection time, the holding pressure and the holding time. The optimum processing parameters for a certain part were not only a function of the thermoplastic used but also a function of the mold geometry.

For every commercially available, injection moldable thermoplastic polymer the processing properties are given in a certain range. Starting from this point, the injection parameters were systematically varied and optimized. The produced samples had a ring geometry with an inner diameter of 80 mm, a width of 20 mm and a wall thickness of 4 mm. The materials used in these investigations were polypropylene (Novolen®, No. 2862 JX, BASF), ABS (Terulan®, No. 211132, BASF) and polyamide (Ultramid®, No. A3W-71133, BASF).

In the next step of this work a filament wound ring with an inner diameter of 80 mm, a width of 20 mm and a thickness of about 1.5 mm was placed as an insert into the same mold, and was then embedded into a thermoplastic polymer. For this process, the injection parameters such as temperature and pressure had to be optimized in order to achieve optimum material properties and strong bonding between insert and injected material.

MATERIALS INVESTIGATED FOR FILAMENT WINDING

Figure 3: Raw materials for thermoplastic filament winding

In the frame these investigations two different tow materials were processed by thermoplastic filament winding. These tows offer a high degree of flexibility in comparison to stiffer tapes, but are more difficult to process by filament winding (Fig. 3).

The first material was a commingled yarn with fibers of polyamide (PA), polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and glass (GF). The GF/PTFE/PA-tow had a thickness of about 170tex. This tow was designed for tribological applications. The wound structure might be useful as a sliding surface in a bearing application.

The second material investigated was a polymer powder impregnated and with a thin polymer matrix sheath surrounded flexible reinforcing fiber bundle. The particular components consisted of glass fibers and a polyethyleneterephthalate matrix material (GF-PET-1200tex).

MATERIAL TESTING METHODS

The tensile strength of the injection molded rings were determined employing a special ring tensile testing device integrated in an universal testing machine (Fig. 4). Furthermore, this test allowed the determination of the tensile modulus. In addition, the ring's flexural modulus was measured in a ring bending test, where the entire ring was situated in a testing device and deformed. From the elastic deformation, the force and the ring's geometry, the flexural modulus could be calculated [4].

Figure 4: Ring tensile testing arrangement

In order to optimize the processing parameters of filament winding, rings with an inner diameter of 146 mm, a width of 12 mm, and a wall thickness of about 3 mm (depending on winding time, tow dimensions and consolidation quality) were analyzed.

An interlaminar shear testing device was developed by Lauke [3]. The interlaminar shear strength of the rings was determined by testing a small segment of the ring having a uniform thickness and a circular arc length along the centerline of about 8 mm. The ring's density was also a very sensitive parameter for the characterization of the consolidation quality of thermoplastic filament wound structures. Because of the very simple geometry of a ring, the density could easily be calculated via the ring's dimensions and its weight. The flexural modulus was investigated by employing a vibration test. During this test, the ring was dropped on a hard surface. Once it bounced back, it started vibrating in its natural frequency (neglecting damping). A strain gage measured the elongation of the ring surface. With the frequency, the ring's geometry, and density, its flexural modulus could be calculated [4]. The residual stresses in the rings were determined as a function of the winding parameters. The experimental set up for the residual stress determination was nearly the same as for the flexural modulus. A strain gage was bonded to the inner ring surface, while at the strain gage's opposite side a small segment was cut out. Caused by its internal stresses, the ring deformed. The surface elongation of the ring was simultaneously measured by the strain gage.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to find the optimum processing window for filament winding, each processing parameter was altered, based on a standard parameter, whereas the others were kept constant. Thus, the influence of each winding parameter on the quality parameters could be evaluated. Exemplary the influences of prewarming temperature and winding speed on the rings' quality are depicted in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Figure 5: Ring's material properties as a function of the temperature of the prewarming chamber

Figure 6: Ring's material properties as a function of winding speed

Fig. 5 shows, that with an increasing prewarming temperature both the density and the flexural modulus were improved. Therefore, 170 °C was the most suitable prewarming temperature for processing of GF-PET-1200tex. Higher prewarming temperatures caused a deterioration of the

matrix material in the following preheating zone. Lower temperatures did not allow a complete impregnation.

The next step of this investigation consisted in an enhancement of the winding speed. Starting from a speed of 12 m/min, the winding speed was gradually increased in steps of 6 m/min up to 30 m/min. For higher winding speeds a shorter time remained for the matrix material to melt and flow between the fibers. Fig. 6 exhibits the ring's interlaminar shear strength and the flexural modulus as a function of winding speed. Higher winding speeds resulted in a lower interlaminar shear strength. Also the composite's density and the flexural modulus decreased with winding speed. These effects were due to the shorter impregnation time, and thus a higher void content in the wound structures.

From the experimental results it could be concluded to what extent the quality of the rings was influenced by various winding parameters. The optimum mandrel temperature was near the polymer's crystallite melting temperature. Lower mandrel temperatures resulted in a poor consolidation quality and higher temperatures led to an overheating and eventually to a degradation of the matrix material. This was also valid for the nip point temperature of which the optimum was found to be above the crystallite melting temperature, therefore also above the mandrel temperature because the wound part was only instantaneously affected by this extra heat input, in opposite to the stationary heating of the mandrel. The tow tension was necessary for the tow guidance onto a predetermined fiber path. This tension was however restricted to a value that was caused by the friction of the tow guidance device and by the maximum stress which could be carried by the tow. For winding of glass fibers a minimum tow tension was recommended in order to introduce only low residual stresses in the rings. With an increasing compaction pressure a better matrix flow could be obtained, which guaranteed a lower void content between the fibers. But also the compaction pressure (consolidation force) had an optimum value. Higher consolidation forces damaged the fibers and caused squeezing of the molten polymer out of the ring's cross section.

For the special winding arrangement investigated, a winding speed of 12 m/min led to the best results in terms of shear strength, modulus, and density. When higher winding speeds were realized, no sufficient time remained for the melting- and consolidation process; in addition, there was not enough time for heat exchange between the hot air and the incoming tow. In case of lower winding speeds, the tow material remained too long in the hot air region of the nip point, so that the matrix material could get degraded at its surface. From the experimental data the optimum processing window could be determined as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Optimal processing window of the in-situ process

Material	Tow Tension [N]	Consolid. Force [N]	Mandrel Temp. [°C]	Nip-Point-Temp. [°C]	Winding Speed [m/min]	Prewarm. Temp. [°C]	Preheat. Temp. [°C]
GF-PET 1200tex	15	450	240	280	12	170	400

For the injection process, the parameters were also optimized by a systematic variation. Exemplary the influence of mass temperature on the ring's material properties is presented in Fig. 6. The absolute values of tensile strength and modulus were lower as it could be expected for the type of polypropylene used (catalogue values: tensile strength 16 MPa, flexural modulus 720 MPa). This fact can be explained by the flow direction during injection molding and the resulting orientation of the molecules perpendicular to the tensile test direction in the rings tested, compared to the standard tensile bars used for determining the catalogue values.

In the range between 180°C and 230°C an increasing mass temperature resulted in a higher tensile strength. The maximum tensile strength for an injection molded PP ring was about 13 MPa. A further increase of the mass temperature resulted in a decrease in tensile strength. Nearly the same results could be observed concerning the ring's tensile and flexural moduli. In this case, the optimum mass temperature was about 210 °C.

Fig. 7 illustrates the bonding quality between the filament wound ring and the surrounding thermoplastic polymer. In the frame of this study the best bonding resulted between the GF-PA-PTFE insert and the injection molded polyamide material around it.

Figure 6: Ring's material properties as a function of mass temperature

This is not surprising because of the same type of matrix in the two components. The subsequent ranking order was also expected, when considering the compatibility tendencies of the various polymers in intimate contact with each other.

Figure 7: Relative bonding quality between filament wound sample and injected material

Very poor bonding could be observed between the polypropylene and the two inserts, for which the bonding quality was only about 20%. For ABS the bonding quality was much better than for PP. Here the values were in the range of 80%.

Concerning the bonding qualities it has to be mentioned, that the insert was placed in the mold under room temperature and was then injected around. Preheating of the insert's surface or its pretreatment with a third compatibilization agent are expected to improve the bonding quality between insert and polymer. These investigations will be performed in the near future.

Fig. 8 shows two different parts, which were produced with this technology. The first one was a ring, where the inner surface was filament wound using a commingled yarn of glass-, PTFE-, and polyamid fibers. The surrounding thermoplastic was polyamide. Such a structure could be used in friction and wear applications.

The second part consist of a very stiff glass-fiber-PBT insert. In this case, a very complex geometry of the surrounding thermoplastic was realized.

Figure 6: Ring compound produced by combined filament winding and injection molding

CONCLUSION

For thermoplastic filament winding and injection molding only slight deviations in process parameters led to great variations in part quality. For both technologies the process parameters were optimized with regard to several quality criteria.

The combination of thermoplastic filament winding and injection molding offered the possibility of producing complex part geometries with functional properties. The advantages of both techniques could be combined.

In the next step of this work, the bonding quality between the insert and the surrounding polymer has to be optimized. One possibility is the preheating of the insert's surface with hot air or an infrared heater immediately before closing the injection mold, another one is pretreatment with a third compatibilization agent adjusted to the two different polymeric matrices in contact.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The support of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft for presentation of this work at ICCM-10, Canada, August 1995 is gratefully acknowledged. Further thanks are due to ARBURG Ltd., Germany for the injection molding machine. Prof. Friedrich, would also like to thank the FONDS DER CHEMISCHEN INDUSTRIE, Frankfurt, for support of his personal research activities in 1995.

REFERENCES

1. F Hauptert, K Friedrich, On Processing and Properties of Rings Wound from Thermoplastic Powder Impregnated Continuous Fiber Composites, *Proc. "Advancing with Composites '94", Milano, Italy, May 2-7, (1994)*
2. F. Hauptert, K. Friedrich, Processing Related Consolidation of High Speed Filament Wound Continuous Fiber / Thermoplastic Composite Rings, *Proc. "Flow Processes in Composite Materials '94", University College Galway, Ireland, July 7-9, (1994)*
3. B. Lauke, K. Schneider, K. Friedrich, Interlaminar Shear Strength Measurement of Thin Composite Rings Fabricated by Filament Winding, *Proc. of ECCM 5, Fifth European Conference on Composite Materials, April 7-10, Bordeaux, France, (1992)*
4. F. Hauptert, K. Friedrich, Characterization of the Consolidation and Impregnation Quality of Thermoplastic Filament Wound Composite Rings, *Proc. "2nd European Conference on Composites", ECCM, Testing and Standardization, Hamburg, September 13-15, (1994)*